

The Chemistry Jute-lignin. Part IX. Acetylation of Lignin.

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In the previous paper it has been shown by the author that no definite conclusion regarding the number of hydroxyl groups in lignin can be drawn from the results of methylation of lignin separated in the usual way, in view of the fact that new OH groups appeared owing to the partial decomposition of the dioxymethylene group present in lignin. It was further pointed out that five additional methyl groups entered the molecule of genuine lignin when it was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali. To confirm the results obtained by the methylation of jute-lignin, it was acetylated.

Like methylation, acetylation results of lignin by different workers seldom agree; many of these do not even corroborate the methylation data. Thus, the maximum methoxyl value of Heuser and co-workers (*Cellulosechem.*, 1921, 2, 80) corresponded to about four OH groups, whilst their acetylation data (*ibid.*, 1924, 5, 13) indicate the presence of six OH groups in the molecule. The acetyl content of HCl-lignin varied considerably with the source of lignin as has been shown by Pringsheim and Mangus (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1919, 105, 179). Various lignins have been acetylated by Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 357), Phillips (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2037) as well as by Fuchs and Horn (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 2647), but their highest acetylation values do not at all agree with one another. It is difficult to say how far it is due to the difference in technique adopted and to what extent to the difference in the source whence the lignin was obtained.

Of the usual methods available for acetylation, acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine was found to be the best, the highest acetyl value being obtained by two successive treatments. The highest acetic acid content has been found to be 26.45%, which means five OH groups in a molecular weight of 830 for lignin, the theoretical value being 28.85%. Thus, in the case of jute-lignin the results of acetylation agree quite well with the methylation data.

As expected, by acetylating ordinary HCl-lignin and genuine lignin after boiling with 28% sulphuric acid for 3-4 hours under reflux, higher percentage of acetic acid was obtained in both cases. The results are shown in Table I.

Reducing lignin (genuine lignin boiled with moderately strong HCl or 28% sulphuric acid) on acetylation no longer reduced ammoniacal silver nitrate, showing conclusively the absence of aldehyde group in jute-lignin. This confirms the previous observation of the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 691) that the reducing action of lignin is due to the presence of 2 hydroxyl groups in the *ortho*-position attached to the benzene rings formed as a result of partial degradation of lignin in respect of its dioxymethylene group. The reducing action of acetylated lignin on Fehling's solution could not be tested because of the fact that the warm caustic alkali hydrolysed the acetyl groups readily and the product reduced Fehling's solution.

The dioxymethylene group has been found to remain unaffected during acetylation, as will be seen from the formaldehyde-content of the acetylated lignin.

Very little improvement in colour was observed on acetylating lignin; so the view of Pringsheim and Mangus (*loc. cit.*) that the dark colour of separated lignin was due to the loss of acetyl group, does not appear to be justified. Nor did the acetylated lignin go into solution in pyridine as was observed by them.

The fact that acetic acid corresponding to five acetyl group entering a molecule of 830 was obtained, lends further support to the author's former view that this figure actually represents the molecular weight of jute-lignin. The methoxyl value (Zeisel's method) of the acetylated product was found to be 15.32%, which shows that all the five methoxyl groups present in original lignin are also present in the acetylated product.

To test for the presence of ethylenic double bond, jute-lignin was shaken mechanically with metallic palladium in a closed chamber containing hydrogen (connected to a manometer) for 4 to 5 hours, but no absorption of hydrogen was observed. This fact further corroborates the results obtained by the author by the chlorination of lignin (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 777) when the ratio of chlorine evolved as HCl to the chlorine combined with the lignin, was shown to be very approximately equal to 1:1.

Attempts to measure the iodine value of lignin as done by Mehta (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 958) with IBr or ICl proved futile as small

amount of these reagents was absorbed by saturated benzene compounds like phenol, anisol, vanillin and others (Table II) and as the results with lignin was too low, and of the same order as with vanillin, it might be inferred that no ethylenic double bond in the side-chain is present in jute-lignin.

The iodoform-yielding complex in jute-lignin appears in all probability to be a side-chain consisting of $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO-}$ or $\text{CH}_3\text{-CHOH-}$ groupings as observed by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 691). Raw jute and HCl-lignin but not delignified jute, gave iodoform at room temperature with iodine and caustic soda. This shows that the iodoform-yielding complex is characteristic of lignin and not of cellulose; and further, this group remains in tact during the isolation of lignin. The distillate obtained by the acid or alkali distillation of jute-lignin, or its chloro-derivative, responded to the colorimetric test for $\text{CH}_3\text{-CO-}$ by Goswami and others (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 773), but it has not yet been possible to identify the volatile substance.

Following the procedure of Böesenken and Sloof (*Proc. Amsterdam Academy of Sci.*, 1932, **35**, 170) who prepared a cyclic compound of pyrocatechol by treating it with acetone in presence of P_2O_5 below 10° , it has been possible to obtain a similar compound with jute-lignin after expelling all the formaldehyde from it in the usual manner. The black starting material became light gray in colour and was no longer soluble in dilute caustic soda. It did not exhibit any reducing property towards Fehling's solution. This proves the presence of two OH groups in the *ortho*-position in lignin formed as a result of the loss of formaldehyde and further corroborates the author's results of methylenation of jute-lignin (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 691).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetylation of jute-lignin.—About 2 g. of very finely powdered jute-lignin (dried at 105°) was heated on a water-bath for 2-3 hours with 25 c.c. of a mixture of acetic anhydride (12 c.c.) and pyridine (88 c.c.). The acetylated product obtained after pouring the solution into water, was washed with water and pyridine. It was dried at 105° . To ensure complete acetylation, the process was repeated a second time.

Estimation of acetic acid.—About 0.5 g. of the finely powdered acetylated product was taken in a flask and 5 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid was added to it, it was corked and shaken from time to time gently to ensure thorough mixing. After 24 hours, 200 c.c. of water were added to it and the liquid distilled in steam very slowly until the distillate was neutral to litmus. To obtain concordant results, it was necessary to use an ammonium distillation bulb in the flask containing the liquid and barium hydroxide in the steam generator. The former prevents any mechanical carriage of sulphuric acid and the latter frees the steam from carbonic acid gas. The distillate was transferred to a measuring flask as soon as possible to avoid absorption of carbon dioxide from air and acetic acid estimated by titration in the usual way.

TABLE I.

Sample acetylated.	Acetic acid.	Mean.
(a) Jute-lignin prepared in the usual way.	32.0 % 33.5	32.75 %
(b) Jute-lignin prepared by the modified method.	28.9 30.0	29.45
(c) Sample (b) boiled with 28% sulphuric acid for 4 hours under reflux.	34.20 35.52	34.86

None of the acetylated products dissolved in any solvent nor melted within 300°. Sample (c) was fairly soluble in dilute caustic soda before acetylation but was insoluble afterwards, showing the absence of free phenolic group.

The methoxyl value of sample (b) was found to be 15.32%; the molecular weight of the acetylated lignin being 1040 (taking 830 as the molecular weight of the original lignin) this figure indicates the presence of 5 methoxyl groups in it. These were also present in the original lignin. Formaldehyde was estimated in the acetylated product by the dimedone method and the yield after solubility correction was 2.16%. This shows that the dioxymethylene group as well remained unaffected during acetylation.

Absorption of IBr and ICl by jute-lignin.—As will be found in the following table, saturated aromatic compounds absorb a small amount of these reagents just like lignin. About 0.3 g. of the substance was taken in a stoppered conical flask and 10 c.c. of IBr or ICl

solution in glacial acetic acid was added and kept for about an hour in a dark place in the usual way. Excess of the reagent was titrated with thiosulphate after adding sufficient KI solution. IBr and ICl behaved similarly. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Substance.	Original titre (thio).	Final titre (thio).	Substance.	Original titre (thio).	Final titre (thio).
Phenol	21.50 c.c.	14.30 c.c.	Resorcinol	20.8 c.c.	10.60 c.c.
Anisol	„	14.20	Aspirin	„	20.20
Benzene	„	21.50	<i>p</i> -Cresol	„	13.4
Vanillin	„	17.55	<i>p</i> -Cresol methyl ether	„	15.0
Benzoic acid	„	21.50	<i>m</i> -Cresol	„	11.45
Piperonylic acid	„	21.45	<i>m</i> -Cresol methyl ether	„	13.70
Lignin	„	17.50	<i>cyclo</i> Hexane	„	20.45
Phloroglucinol	„	9.0	<i>cyclo</i> Hexanol	„	16.10

SUMMARY.

1. By the acetylation of jute-lignin, it has been shown that it contains 5 OH groups; methylation and acetylation results agree very well.

2. Acetylation value of genuine lignin further confirms the view that jute-lignin has a mol. wt. of 830.

3. As the acetylated lignin no longer shows any reducing action, it is concluded that jute-lignin contains no aldehyde group.

4. As jute-lignin absorbs no hydrogen in presence of metallic palladium, it is inferred that it has no ethylene linkage.

5. Slight absorption of IBr or ICl by jute-lignin does not prove the presence of a double bond in the side-chain.

6. Acetone compound of jute-lignin has been prepared, which corroborates the author's view regarding the O-CH₂-O group in lignin as shown by the methylenation of jute-lignin.

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